

IMPREGNATION STRATEGIES FOR GRADIENT FUNCTIONALIZATION OF FRP STRUCTURES WITH NANOPARTICLE-MODIFIED RESIN SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction of nanoparticles (NPs) is a promising way to effectively improve the performance of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) structures or to introduce certain functionalities to them. This is especially attractive for impregnation processes, which allow for low-cost production of high-performance FRPs. The effectiveness of NPs is dependent on the chemical and physical characteristics. However, depending on these characteristics, NPs affect the critical impregnation processing aspects such as rheology and fiber-preform permeability, which may negatively influence the pot life of the matrix or the impregnation length. Therefore, innovative impregnation strategies are essential to achieve an optimal balance between the process and final properties. Impregnation with selective NP-modified resin systems enables an optimal gradient-functionalized FRP structure regarding the stress gradient during application, which still guarantees production efficiency. In this paper, firstly, flow and retention behavior of two NPs – boehmite and silica – are investigated by design of experiment methods. According to the maximum flow length and NP gradient, different sequential and parallel impregnation strategies with multiple inlet/outlet positions are put forward. Finally, flow simulations are carried out regarding the sequential and parallel impregnation strategies, by which the position of the inlet/outlet positions can be designed to increase the process robustness.

1 INTRODUCTION

By introducing effective NPs into the FRPs, the properties/functionalities – including fracture toughness, electrical/thermal conductivity, magnetic properties, frictional and wear performance, surface quality etc. of the structures can be tailored [1-6]. Nevertheless, depending on the types and concentration, the NPs might show some adverse effects of on the critical impregnation parameters, e.g. accelerated curing behavior, increased viscosity and even retention behavior of NPs, which may negatively influence the pot life of the matrix or the impregnation length [7, 8].

In most applications of FRP structures, there is mostly a certain stress gradient – according to the application load conditions. The regions that face the highest stress condition dictate the application stability and the final strength of the whole structure. For instance, many stringer, rib or spar structures are used in large-scale structures – e.g. airplane fuselage, wing panel etc. – to resist the bending and axial loads along the skin. The structures are characterized by the remarkably large longitudinal dimension, which puts a great challenge for impregnation process.

Synergistically considering the application requirements on the properties and functionalities of the FRP structures and the influence of NPs on the process, innovative impregnation strategies are essential to achieve an optimal balance between the process and final properties. Impregnation with selective NP-modified resin systems enables an optimal gradient-functionalized FRP structure regarding the stress gradient during application, which still guarantees production efficiency by minimizing the negative effects of NPs on the impregnation processes. The concept of multi-scale gradient with NPs in the FRPs regarding the stress gradient is illustrated in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: Gradient functionalization of FRP structure with NPs regarding the stress gradient

2 MATERIALS

2.1 Boehmite-epoxy nanosuspension

Boehmite NPs (primary particle size of 20nm, Sasol Germany) are dispersed into the epoxy matrix to produce masterbatches with 40 wt% boehmite NPs, at the Institute for Particle Technology (IPAT)-TU Braunschweig. The x10%, x50% and x90% values of dispersed particle size within the produced masterbatch are separately 81 nm, 104 nm and 134 nm, as shown in Figure 2.

2.2 Fiber reinforcement

A quasi-unidirectional carbon-fiber (CF) textile (Style 796) from Fa. ECC is used. The textile has an average areal weight of 270 g/m² (warp/0° direction: 400 tex carbon fiber, weft/90° direction: 34 tex glass fiber for stabilization), as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Particle size distribution of boehmite nanosuspension

Figure 3: Quasi-unidirectional carbon-fiber textile (Fa. ECC, Style 796)

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Influence of particle retention behavior on permeability

As shown in the following Figure 4, it is obvious that, depending on the preform compaction state and fiber direction, the NPs show different flow and retention characteristics, which have remarkable influence on the preform permeability. It is therefore of big interest to develop and design optimal impregnation strategies depending on the particle size distribution characteristics, textile compaction behavior and structural complexity.

Figure 4: Boehmite NP concentration along flow length by different FVF. Parallel to fiber (left) and transverse to fiber direction (right)

By permeability measurements with standard fluids (incompressible flow) at constant pressure, the development of flow front (x_f^2) versus time (t) shows a linear increase with a constant slope, as shown in Figure 5 (linear regression). However, for particle-filled systems, if the particles could deposit during the flow, it could lead to changes of fluid density and textile porosity, leading to a gradual deviation of the flow front from linearity, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Flow front development in a permeability measurement by incompressible flow (oil or pure epoxy)

Figure 6: Flow front development in a permeability measurement by compressible flow (FVF60%, 5wt% nanosuspension)

After experimental and numerical investigation, it is found out that the development of x_f^2 versus t by a particle-filled fluid could be mathematically well described by an exponential decay function in increasing form as following,

$$y = a(1 - \exp(-bx)) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Therein, a is the maximum limit and b is the decay factor. The exponential decay function curve development regarding the different coefficient values are illustrated in the following Figure 7, in comparison with linear development. In the case of the flow of NP-filled fluid in textiles, the parameter a – maximum limit – represents the maximum quadratic flow length, and the parameter b – decay factor – represents the NP filtration or gradient factor.

Figure 7: The exponential decay function curve development depending on the parameters

3.2 Permeability based on NP-epoxy suspension: Design of Experimental (DoE) studies

Due to the particle retention during the injection, the permeability could be influenced by fiber volume fraction (FVF), NP concentration and other process parameters, including viscosity (temperature) and pressure. If the particles are filtrated, the permeability is a decreasing function of flow length. Therefore, the maximum flow length and filtration factor are important parameters that are critical for injection process and design of injection strategies. In order to investigate and find out the relationship between the factors, responses and runs, statistical DoE methods could be applied. In order to investigate the effect of FVF, NP concentration, temperature and pressure to the flow and filtration behavior – as response, a response surface method (RSM) is applied with 2nd interaction and 2nd power effects. The critical factors and their level are listed below in Table 1 and Table 2. In order to prevent the evaluation errors due to the deviation in the parameters, the actual measured average values of FVF, temperature and pressure are used for the evaluations. Other parameters, temperature and pressure, is selected considering the viscosity and commonly used industrial parameters in RTM processes.

Table 1: Critical factors and their levels by experimental design for permeability/flow length study (NP-epoxy suspension)

Factors	Level			Response
	1	2	3	
FVF (%)	50	55	60	Flow length & filtration factor
NP (wt%)	0	2.5	5	
Temperature (°C)	60	80	100	
Pressure (bar)	1	2	3	

Table 2: Experimental design using the RSM method with interaction and power effects (NP-epoxy suspension)

Exp. No.	FVF %	NP Wt%	Temperature (°C)	Pressure (bar)	Response	Fit Model	
1	60	5	100	3		Effects(:FVF %, :FVF % * :FVF %, :NP Wt%, :NP Wt% * :NP Wt%, :Temperature, :Temperature * :Temperature, :Pressure,	Single & quadratic effects
2	60	0	60	3			
3	50	0	100	1			
4	60	5	60	3			
5	60	5	60	1			
6	55	0	60	1			
7	60	0	100	2			
8	55	2.5	80	2			
9	50	5	100	1			

10	60	5	100	1		:FVF % * :NP Wt%, :FVF % * :Temperature, :FVF % * :Pressure, :NP Wt% * :Temperature, :NP Wt% * :Pressure, :Temperature * :Pressure) Y(:Permeability)	Second order interactions
11	60	0	80	1			
12	50	5	60	1			
13	50	5	100	3			
14	50	5	60	3			
15	55	0	100	3			
16	50	0	60	2			
17	50	0	80	3			

For the first step, a parameter screening evaluation is carried out. The results are provided as in the Figure 8 and Figure 9 below. According to the probability value— P value as shown in the Figure 8, a low p-value (a value less than 0.05) indicates that results are statistically significant, which are identified by the color and asterisks. It is also obvious that NP-concentration, FVF, temperature and their interactions all have a significant influence for the response value (maximal flow length). This can be further verified by the half-normal probability plot of effects as shown in the Figure 9—all the effects that lie along the line are negligible, whereas the larger effects deflect away from the line.

Figure 8: ANOVA analysis for the parameters screening by DoE studies for NP-epoxy suspension

Figure 9: Half normal probability plot of effects by DoE studies for NP-epoxy suspension

The DoE studies from the NP-epoxy suspension show that the flow behavior of the particle-filled matrix system is dependent on many factors, and is correspondingly much more complex. Yet, by the DoE study, an experimental model for flow length and filtration factor could be developed, with the critical parameters and their interactions, which could be used for designing impregnation strategies and other parameters.

3.1 Impregnation strategies and flow simulation

Impregnation strategies are designed depending on the structure geometry, maximum impregnation time/length of the matrix, as well as efficiency and complexity of the process. Conventionally, the target function is mostly the impregnation time or impregnation quality (impregnation velocity, converging flow fronts etc.), with impregnation time/length of the matrix as boundary conditions. However, to fabricate gradient FRP structures with NP-filled matrix, comes the maximum flow length by different NP-epoxy matrix systems as a critical boundary condition to design an optimal impregnation strategy.

Considering the flow and filtration behavior of the NP, textile compaction state, fiber direction and flow length, it is possible to design proper process step sequences and impregnation strategies and achieve the desired gradient in the structure. First of all, two different impregnation methods, in-plane and out-of-plane, can be differentiated. By the in-plane impregnation process, as illustrated in Figure 10, the textiles are placed in a closed mold, and the matrix is injected from one size as linear (1D) or from the middle as radial flow (2D) form. The fluid flows in-plane homogeneously within the textile to the outlet direction. In comparison, by the out-of-plane impregnation process (see Figure 11), a gap or a high permeable flow medium is adjusted above/under the textile, by which the fluid will quickly flow

through the flow media and impregnate the laminate in the thickness direction due to the high permeability difference between the flow media and compacted textiles. There are different variations of out-of-plane impregnation methods, including Compaction Resin Transfer Molding (CRTM) or Gap Impregnation etc. The out-of-plane impregnation methods are advantageous considering the very short impregnation length, especially considering particle-filled high-viscous suspensions. However, the out-of-plane impregnation processes are not as flexible and robust as the in-plane impregnation methods for impregnation of complex geometrical structures.

Figure 10: Illustration of in-plane impregnation process

Figure 11: Illustration of out-of-plane impregnation process

For impregnation of complex geometries, in-plane impregnation is preferable, where the maximum flow length and filtration factor are important for designing the inlet/outlet positions. Based on the maximum flow length and filtration factor, optimal injection strategies regarding the desired NP gradient and structure complexity can be tailored. Several different in-plane injection strategies can be illustrated with the following two most representative injection strategies, as shown below: sequential and parallel injection. By sequential injection, multiple injection gates could be designed with the desired distance, according to the NP gradient and flow length. As long as the flow front reaches the nearby injection gate, the first gate closes and the second gate opens. In comparison, by the parallel injection, all the injection gates simultaneously could be opened. In both cases, NP-epoxy suspensions with different particle types or concentrations could be applied to adjust the optimal gradient profile in the structure, considering the maximum flow length and NP gradient factor.

The impregnation concepts and particle gradient can be visualized by applying different color agents in the epoxy. As shown in the Figure 13, two different kinds of materials are injected from both sides simultaneously (left: red, right: blue), representing different kinds of NPs or concentrations to gradually modify the property profile of the structure.

Figure 12: In-plane linear impregnation strategies: sequential injection and parallel injection

Figure 13: Visualization of in-plane parallel impregnation strategy

Flow simulation is rather important in LCM processes, considering the high possibility of the potential impregnation failures – dry spots, air bubbles inclusion, which are quite critical for the product qualities but often happens due to the closed nature of the mold where the filling/impregnation state is hard to be observed or controlled manually. Especially, in the case of NP-filled matrix systems, the flow simulation is especially important considering the retention behavior of the NPs, which could strongly influence on the impregnation length. The following Figure 14 shows the preliminary results regarding prediction of the flow front position combining the sequential and parallel impregnation strategies, applying the simplified permeability model. The flow simulation supports the design of inlet/outlet positions and increases the process robustness remarkably.

Figure 14: Flow simulation. Sequential injection (top) and parallel injection (bottom)

4 CONCLUSIONS

Depending on the fiber preform compaction state and fiber direction, NPs show different flow and retention behavior, which have remarkable influence on preform permeability, which may negatively influence the maximum impregnation length. In this work, firstly, the permeability behavior of the preform is modelled with a new model with two characteristic parameters – maximum flow length and particle retention factor. Accordingly, depending on the NP retention behavior, textile compaction behavior and stress gradient in the structure, different sequential and parallel impregnation strategies with multiple inlet/outlet positions are put forward according to the maximum flow length and NP gradient. Finally, flow simulations regarding the sequential and parallel impregnation strategies are carried out to predict the flow front development by complex flow scenarios.

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